

A Study on Characterisation of some Pillared Clays

BALDEV SINGH^a, SUBHASH CHANDRA RAY^a, K. P. SHARMA^a, SISIR KUMAR ROY^a and P. BANDOPADHYAY^b

^a Central Fuel Research Institute, P.O. FRI, Dhanbad-828 108

^b Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad-826 004

Manuscript received 10 July 1992, revised 16 March 1993, accepted 14 May 1993

Attempts have been made to characterise pillared clay catalysts by different physicochemical techniques, like MAS NMR spectroscopy, DTA, ammonia TPD and also by measuring the surface-area. Ammonia TPD indicates the generation of strong acid sites on pillaring. The MAS NMR spectra of the clay catalysts reveal that both tetrahedral and octahedral aluminium are present. It is also concluded that during the formation of pillared clays, there is interaction between tetrahedral layer of the clay and the Al-oligomer forming weak bonds.

Acid-treated and cation-exchanged montmorillonite clay minerals have been shown to possess an ability to promote organic reactions as acid catalyst¹. Clay catalysts are industrially used petroleum cracking catalysts, although they are superseded by amorphous silica-alumina and zeolite catalysts because of the lack of thermal stability at high temperature. Recently developed methods for cross-linking of clays using polycationic compounds, however, have provided a new class of molecular sieves which are structurally different from zeolites. Cross-linked clays thus prepared are called pillared interlayer clays (PILC) and they have high thermal stability and surface area.

Pillared clays have been investigated as acid catalysts for various reactions. Literature^{2,3} on the detailed characterisation of the pillared clays are scanty, hence attempts have been made to characterise the pillared clays by DTA, MAS NMR spec-

troscopy, ammonia TPD and determining the surface area.

Results and Discussion

The surface area of the clay catalysts increases significantly on pillaring with inorganic salts (e.g. S.A. of montmorillonite clay = 16.8 m² g⁻¹, S.A. of montmorillonite clay pillared with Zr-salt = 90.8 m² g⁻¹)⁴. DTA curves (not shown) of original montmorillonite as well as Al-pillared montmorillonite clay (pillared with Al-oligomer) reveal a sharp endothermic peak at about 124°, may be due to loss of water. In case of Al-pillared clay the water is also lost at about 124° with a broad endothermic peak, this may be due to solvation of the pillaring polyoxocations⁵.

Three clay samples, namely, montmorillonite clay, montmorillonite clay pillared with Zr-oligomer, Rajasthan bentonite clay pillared with Al-

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL SHIFT VALUES δ (PPM)

Sl no.	Clay catalyst	²⁷ Al	²⁹ Si
1.	Montmorillonite clay (imported)	8.2915, 46.7916	-40.9863, -92.6743 -106.638, -143.685
2.	Montmorillonite clay (imported) pillared with hydroxy-Zr-oligomer	8.8122, 47.3020, 63.3514, 93.3714, 104.8741, -13.4461, -33.1270	-44.3297, -44.4034, -96.2252, -96.6186, -109.58, -148.208
3.	Rajasthan bentonite clay (India) after pillaring with hydroxy-Al-oligomer	9.4630, 50.7514, 59.7718, 89.8790, 99.2309, -12.6781	-86.0727, -86.1705, -96.9518, -97.183, -97.3315, -97.4298

oligomer are characterised by MAS NMR spectroscopy. The ^{27}Al and ^{29}Si NMR spectral shift values of the above clays are shown in Table 1. From the chemical shift values of ^{27}Al nucleus, the presence of both octahedral and tetrahedral aluminium have been observed. MAS NMR spectra of the clay pillared with Al-oligomer (heated at 400° for 4 h) is conspicuous with the absence of the resonance corresponding to the tetrahedral aluminium of the pillar. In addition, the peaks are very much broadened. ^{29}Si bands are also very much broadened. The peak broadening of silica bands may be due to a consequence of quadrupolar aluminium interaction. From the MAS NMR spectra of the pillared clays it may be inferred that both Lewis and Bronsted acid sites of varying extent are present.

Fig. 1. TPD pattern of montmorillonite.

The MAS NMR spectra of the Al-pillared clay (baked at 400°) showed similar pattern of the Al-pillared beidelite as obtained by Plee *et al.*⁶. The resonance due to the tetrahedral aluminium of Al_{13} oligomer is apparent at 62.3 ppm. Upon calcining

Fig. 2. TPD pattern of montmorillonite after pillaring with hydroxy-Al-oligomeric solution.

the Al-pillared Rajasthan bentonite, the ^{27}Al MAS NMR spectrum is greatly modified. No defined peak corresponding to chemical shift expected for the tetrahedral aluminium of the pillar was observed. Moreover, the intensity of resonance of the tetrahedral aluminium in the layer is greatly decreased. Thus it may be inferred that during pillaring there is interaction between Al_{13} oligomer and the tetrahedral layer of the clay. The tetrahedral layer may be linked with the pillaring aggregate by the formation of weak bonds.

For the precursor pillared montmorillonite, the silicon signal in the ^{29}Si MAS NMR spectra is at $(-)$ 93.5 ppm, whereas after calcination this shifts to $(-)$ 95.5 ppm correspond to the formation of neutral layered structure. The neutrality is produced by the hydrogen ions generated during the calcination process migrating to the octahedral layers. Similar pattern for ^{29}Si MAS NMR spectra for the calcined Zr-pillared montmorillonite and Al-pillared bentonite were observed.

The ammonia TPD histograms of pure montmorillonite, Al-pillared montmorillonite and Zr-pillared montmorillonite clays are shown in Figs 1–3. It is observed that on pillaring medium and strong acid sites increase. In case of the Zr-pillared clays the concentration of strong acid sites were more than that of Al-pillared clays.

Fig. 3. TPD pattern of montmorillonite after pillaring with hydroxy-Zr-oligomeric solution.

Besides the total acidity measurement, the histograms indicate the distribution of strong, medium and weak acid sites. TPD histogram for montmorillonite clay indicates acidity of 0.163 meq ammonia/g with a greater distribution of weak acidic sites upto 55%, medium acidic sites upto 33% and the

rest corresponds to strong acidic sites of 12%. Fig. 2 shows that the pillaring of said montmorillonite clay with Al-oligomer changes the distribution of strong, medium and weak acidic sites with an increase of total acidity of 0.199 meq ammonia/g while the weak acidic sites of Al-pillared clay correspond to nearly 49%, the moderately strong acidic sites increase upto 40.8% with a consequent decrease of strong acidic sites 10.2%. Though the total acidity of Zr-pillared clay remains practically the same to that of Al-pillared clay, there is a marked variation in the distribution of the strong, medium and weak acidic sites. Thus it is evident from Fig. 3 that there is decrease in weak acidic sites with consequent increase of moderately strong acidic sites for Zr-pillared clay. While the weak acidic sites correspond to 41.3%, the moderately strong acidic sites increase upto 45%. Thus it may be inferred that the pillaring of montmorillonite clay either with aluminium or zirconium, oxyocations increases both the total acidity as well as changes the distribution of acidic sites.

The mechanism of generation of acid sites on pillaring of montmorillonite and bentonite clays is explained as follows. Plee *et al.*^{6,8} proposed that on beidelite, the Al_3 species can react with the layer sheet by the inversion of an aluminium tetrahedron, which would then create on Si-O-Al linkage similar to that of zeolites. This site could be a source of the strong acidity observed on such systems.

The remarkable thermal stability of Zr_4 and Al_{13} pillared smectites has been attributed to the formation of metaloxide clusters upon dehydroxylation of the hydroxycations at elevated temperature⁹. In the case of Al_{13} -montmorillonite, the overall interlayer reaction may be written as :

Thus during calcination of the pillared clays there is generation of protonic acid sites.

Experimental

The chemical analysis of the original clay, i.e. montmorillonite and bentonite used for the preparation of the pillared clays are given in Table 2.

The pillared clays were prepared by the reaction of Na^+ -form of the montmorillonite clay minerals with a solution of the polyoxocation of aluminium and zirconium. The ion-exchange method has been followed for the preparation of PILC. The method employed for the preparation is described elsewhere⁷. The pillared clays thus prepared were characterised by DTA, MAS NMR spectroscopy, ammonia TPD and by determining the surface area.

A Dupont 9000 differential thermal analyser was used to study DTA of the catalysts (rate of heating, $10^\circ/min$) using $\alpha-Al_2O_3$ as reference material. MAS NMR spectra of these clay samples were recorded in a Varian XL 400 spectrometer equipped with multinuclear accessories and solid state facilities (Central Research Institute for Chemistry, Budapest, Hungary). The following NMR standards were maintained : for ^{27}Al nuclear frequency 104 MHz, standard $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ and for ^{29}Si nuclear frequency 79 MHz, standard $Si(CH_3)_4$.

The ammonia TPD spectra were taken from Servotrace of Sefram (Paris), model no. PF 7547 recorder in Intersmat instrument chromatograph of GC 12 M. The clay samples (0.1–0.2 g) were taken in a glass tube reactor. Helium gas was passed at 20 $ml\ min^{-1}$ flow rate and at 2 bar pressure. The programming of temperature was done as follows. The temperature was raised from room temperature to 120° in 12 min, then kept constant for 1 h. The temperature was raised to 500° at the rate of 5° per min and kept at this temperature for 4 h. The temperature was then brought down to 50° . The system was then evacuated for 15 min and ammonia gas was passed over the catalyst at 2 bar pressure for 15 min.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE CLAYS

Clay	Analysis %										% loss of ignition at 800°
	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	CaO	MgO	
Montmorillonite	53.6	15.79	6.91	0.51	Tr	Tr	Tr	5.49	1.33	3.56	12.97
Bentonite (Rajasthan)	45.0	16.42	17.86	1.0	1.58	0.30	0.28	Tr	1.20	0.43	21.36

The ammonia from the system except the adsorbed one was flushed out by applying vacuum in catharometer. This was continued for 30 min and then the vacuum was stopped. The desorption of ammonia gas was started from 50 to 500° at 50° interval, while continuing the flow of helium. The desorbed gases at the end were adsorbed in 0.001 N H₂SO₄ which was titrated against 0.001 N NaOH using phenolphthalein as indicator.

The surface area of the clay catalysts were determined by using BET apparatus by nitrogen adsorption at liquid nitrogen temperature.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Dr. Lajos Radics and Dr. P. Sandor, Central Research Institute for Chemistry, Budapest, Hungary, for supplying the MAS NMR spectra, Prof. L. Guzzi, Institute of Isotopes and Prof. D. Kallo, Central Research Institute for Chemistry, Budapest, Hungary, for valuable discussions, Prof. M. Guisnet, Laboratoire de Chimie VII Poitiers, France, for keen interest and useful suggestion, and Mr. Philip Arroult for his help during TPD experiments. The authors are thankful to the authorities of Indo-Hungarian Exchange Programme, and CSIR (India) – CNRS

(France) Exchange Programme for providing facilities to two of them (S.C.R. and K.P.S. respectively). The authors also thank Director, Central Fuel Research Institute, for permission to publish the paper.

References

1. J. A. BALLANTINE, "Chemical Reactions in Organic and Inorganic Constrained System" in NATA ASI Series, Ser. C 165, 1985, p. 197.
2. W. JONES, *Catal. Today*, 1988, **2**, 357.
3. "Chemical Reactions in Organic and Inorganic Constrained System", ed. R. SETTON, 1986, p. 151–164.
4. S. C. ROY, B. SINGH, P. K. SARKAR, S. K. ROY and P. BANDOPADHYAY, unpublished work.
5. T. J. PINNAVAIA, M. TZOU, S. D. LANDAU and R. H. RAYTHATHA, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1984, **27** 195.
6. D. PLEE, A. BORG, L. GATINEAU and J. J. FRIPIAT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **107**, 2362.
7. G. JOHANSSON, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1960, **14**, 771.
8. D. PLEE, A. SCHULZ, G. PONCELET and J. J. FRIPIAT in "Catalysis by Acids and Bases", ed. B. IMELIK, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1985, p. 343.
9. T. J. PINNAVAIA, *Science*, 1983, **220**, 365.